

CoAct Method Submission Template for the CSS Toolkit

1. **Method title (75 characters max):** Self-Assessment Survey for Citizen Social Science Projects
2. **Author:** Barbara Kieslinger, Teresa Schaefer, Katja Mayer, Stefanie Schuerz
3. **Organization:** ZSI - Center for Social Innovation
4. **Related step from the research cycle:** Co-evaluation
Should be undertaken at least twice during the research cycle: Once after first activities have been implemented, once towards or after the end of the project.
5. **Related topic from the research cycle:** Ethics, co-evaluation
6. **Keywords (3-5):** Co-evaluation, Impact assessment
7. **Time needed:** 1-3 hours
8. **Group size:** less than 5 people / 5-10 people
9. **Materials:**

Basic (room, chairs, tables) and Technical (computers/smartphones, Wi-Fi, camera, communication software)

10. Short description of the method (750 characters max):

The Self-Assessment Survey was designed specifically for Citizen Social Science projects and adapted from the self-assessment questionnaire for Citizen Science projects by Kieslinger et al. (2018). It is intended as a self-reflection tool for CSS projects and is best filled in the course of a group conversation. It triggers reflection by jointly rating a series of statements that relate to three main areas: 1) the scientific process, 2) citizens & engaged actors and 3) socio-ecological aspects. In each of these three areas, statements are rated on a Likert scale from 0 ("not at all") to 7 ("fully"). They reflect on the perceived process of implementation as well as expected outcomes and impacts.

11. Aim: What is the aim of this method?

The aim of the Self-Assessment Survey is to trigger a reflection on the process of implementing Citizen Social Science as well as on its impacts across the involved stakeholders. It can be undertaken at the beginning, during and towards/after the end of a project. Thus, it may help adjust a project's trajectory during its runtime and evaluate its impact after its activities have largely been implemented. When used at a very early stage, it can also support the planning and alignment of project activities and goals.

12. Who to involve: Who does this method involve?

Ideally, the Self-Assessment Survey is undertaken by a mixed group of involved stakeholders, including professional researchers, co-researchers, and possibly even members of the otherwise involved stakeholder community. As the content of the survey refers to all of these stakeholder groups, the negotiation process between these actors is highly valuable to the assessment of the project at hand.

13. Further materials: Are there any further materials? Briefly describe the use of the above listed materials and/or include any additional, specific information that users may need.

The Self-Assessment Survey has been set up as an online questionnaire. As such, a computer is needed to fill out the survey. While the answers are given in scores, it can be valuable to document the discussion as important aspects of the project will pop up. The Self-Assessment conversations can take place both physically or in an online meeting space.

14. Step-by-step: What are the individual steps of this method? (list the actions to apply this method).

The Self-Assessment Survey is an online questionnaire that is filled in question by question. It is preferable to have a facilitator to read the questions out loud and mediate the conversation, but it is not necessary. Open fields can be filled with discussion notes and conversations can be recorded to ease note-taking.

15. (Optional) Open field: does this method require a specific section? If so, give us a section title (max 3 words) and related description on the method.

No specific section necessary

16. Documents: Are there any downloads that this method is linked to?

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/17u6lwqQQjblOzkYzfi20uGbtRzwPf2SCy6MmWcOdnDQ/edit#>

17. Gallery: Please add related images (max 5).

No images